

THE IMPORTANCE OF RADIOLOGICAL EXAMINATION IN AMNESIA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19382878>

Abstract

This thesis analyzes the diagnostic importance of radiological examination methods in the development of amnesia syndrome. Amnesia is a neurological condition that occurs as a result of various etiological factors, and modern radiological methods play an important role in identifying its pathophysiological mechanisms. Using computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and functional neuroimaging techniques, morphological and functional changes in brain structures can be detected. Studies show that radiological diagnostics are important for identifying the etiological causes of amnesia, making differential diagnoses, and determining treatment strategies.

Keywords

amnesia, radiological diagnostics, magnetic resonance imaging, computed tomography, hippocampus, brain injury, neuroimaging.

Relevance of the Study

Amnesia is a neurological syndrome characterized by partial or complete impairment of memory function. It may develop as a result of traumatic brain injury, cerebrovascular disorders, degenerative diseases, infections, and metabolic disorders. According to the World Health Organization, cognitive impairments associated with neurological diseases are one of the major global health problems. In recent years, the widespread use of radiological examination methods in diagnostics has significantly expanded the possibilities for identifying the etiological causes of amnesia. Therefore, studying the importance of radiological examinations in the diagnosis of amnesia remains an actual scientific issue.

Main Part

According to clinical studies, approximately 20–30% of patients experience some degree of amnesia after traumatic brain injury. Memory impairment is also observed in about 10–15% of patients who have suffered a stroke. In Alzheimer's disease, amnesia is one of the main clinical manifestations and occurs in more than 70% of cases.

Amnesia may occur due to various etiological factors. The most common causes include traumatic brain injuries, cerebrovascular disorders such as stroke, degenerative diseases particularly Alzheimer's disease, brain tumors, infections of the central nervous system, and toxic or metabolic disorders. These factors can damage brain structures responsible for the formation and storage of memory, leading to impairment of memory processes. In some cases, psychological trauma, adverse effects of medications, or long-term alcohol consumption may also contribute to the development of amnesia.

The development of amnesia is mainly associated with damage to brain structures responsible for the formation and storage of memory. In particular, injury to the hippocampus, limbic system, thalamus, and frontal lobes leads to disturbances in memory processes. Circulatory disorders, neuronal degeneration, or traumatic damage in these structures disrupt synaptic connections, resulting in memory impairment.

Radiological examination methods play an important role in the diagnosis of amnesia. The most commonly used techniques are computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). CT is useful for detecting brain injuries, hemorrhages, and tumors, while MRI provides high accuracy in identifying structural changes in brain regions associated with memory, particularly the hippocampus and the limbic system. In addition, modern neuroimaging techniques such as functional MRI (fMRI), positron emission tomography (PET), and single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) allow evaluation of brain activity and metabolic processes. These imaging methods are essential for identifying the etiological causes of amnesia, performing differential diagnosis, and determining appropriate treatment strategies.

Results

Radiological examination methods make it possible to detect morphological and functional changes in brain structures associated with amnesia. MRI is particularly valuable in identifying damage to the hippocampus and limbic system, while CT is effective for detecting traumatic injuries and acute hemorrhages.

Conclusion

Radiological examination methods play a significant role in the diagnosis of amnesia. Modern neuroimaging technologies allow clinicians to identify the etiological causes of the disease, perform differential diagnosis, and choose appropriate treatment strategies. The combined use of MRI, CT, and functional imaging techniques ensures high diagnostic accuracy in detecting pathological processes associated with amnesia.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Haines D., Mihailoff G. **Fundamental Neuroscience for Basic and Clinical Applications**. Elsevier, 2018.
2. Bradley W. **Neurology in Clinical Practice**. Butterworth-Heinemann, 2020.
3. Blumenfeld H. **Neuroanatomy Through Clinical Cases**. Oxford University Press, 2021.
4. Barkovich A.J. **Pediatric Neuroimaging**. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins, 2019.
5. World Health Organization. **Neurological Disorders: Public Health Challenges**. WHO Press.
6. Squire L.R., Zola-Morgan J.T. **The Cognitive Neuroscience of Human Memory Since H.M.** Annual Review of Neuroscience, 2011.
7. Smith E.E., Kosslyn S.M. **Cognitive Psychology: Mind and Brain**. Pearson Education, 2018